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Chemical composition of acclimatized ginkgo biloba in Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The use of plants for medicine has gradually been refined over the generations and has become known in many countries as traditional medicine. According to WHO(2000), traditional medicine encompasses the total of knowledge, skills and practices based on the beliefs and experiences of indigenous to different cultures, whether explicable or not, used in the maintenance of health, as well as in the prevention, diagnoses, improvement or treatment of physical and mental illness. Over 80 % of the world`s population depends on medicinal plants for better health (K Essandoh, etc, 2023).*

Keywords. *Acclimatized, flafonoid, antiallergic, excitator, antioxidant, anticancer activiti, Parkinson*

Химический состав акклиматизированного гинкго билоба в Узбекистане

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Аннотация. *Использование растений в медицине постепенно совершенствовалось на протяжении поколений и стало известно во многих странах как традиционная медицина. По данным ВОЗ (2000), традиционная медицина включает в себя совокупность знаний, навыков и практик, основанных на верованиях и опыте представителей различных культур, объяснимых или нет, используемых для поддержания здоровья, а также для профилактики диагнозов. , улучшение или лечение физических и психических заболеваний. Здоровье более 80 % населения мира зависит от лекарственных растений (К. Эссандо и др., 2023 г.).*

Ключевые слова. *Акклиматизированное, флафоноидное, противоаллергическое, возбуждающее, антиоксидантное, противораковое действие, Паркинсон,*

The adaptation of local populations and their resilience to the various social, economic, and environmental changes they suffer cannot be understood without considering their ability to interact with the natural environment, which is the product of knowledge transmitted over many generations. This interrelationship between habits, beliefs, and natural resource management, which Folke (Cando D. P. and Maqueda R. H. 2023). *G. biloba* has been used as a traditional medicinal plant for longer than 2000 years in China and other parts of the world (B. Singh etc, 2008) and is currently grown in Europe, Asia, Argentina, North America, and New Zealand (S. R. Tarun etc, 2019). *Ginkgo bicolor* is a gymnosperm relict plant, class Coniferopsida (cone-nosed), order Ginkgoales (*ginkgo*), genus *Ginkgo*, includes the only modern species *Ginkgo biloba* L.

It is known that the *Ginkgo biloba* tree has a very ancient history of more than 200 million years (Bampalia E. 2021). Several chemical compounds have been derived from *G. biloba* with a wide range of therapeutic activities (Liu. L. 2021). It is necessary to thoroughly study the chemical composition of the organs of this medicinal tree and analyze the mechanism of its effect on the body. We believe that the use of *Ginkgo biloba* is an effective solution to one of the major challenges currently facing the WHO. Active chemical components found in *G. biloba* leaves include flavonoids and terpenoids, and plant extracts have exhibited a variety of pharmacological activities, including antibacterial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, and cytotoxic anticancer activities (Chan P. C. 2007). The rapid progression of neurodegenerative diseases occurring within the general population has highlighted the increased need for research to identify the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative disease and develop alternative therapies. Excitatory toxicity is a primary cause of intracerebral neuron death. Neurodegenerative disorders may be prevented by enhancing the cerebral blood supply. *G. biloba* prevents pathological hyperactivity, allowing the body to reclaim its natural physiological equilibrium. In addition, terpenoids and flavonoids in *G. biloba* seeds have been shown to improve blood circulation in the brain (Wang H. Y. 2019). People have always coexisted with plants and reaped their therapeutic and nutritional benefits (Yaagoubi W. E. 2023). The plant is rich in many groups of chemical compounds, terpene trilactones (e.g. *ginkgolides* A, B, C, J, *bilobalides*), flavonoids (*flavonols*, *flavones-isorhamnetin*, *kaempferol*, *quercetin*), organic acids and inorganic ingredients (Lopez-Gutierrez N, 2016).

The number of people suffering from diseases of the central nervous system, including encephalopathy, is increasing among the population worldwide (Селина М.В.. 2017). As a result of microcirculation disorders, cognitive activity in humans is impaired. In Europe, neurological diseases account for 35% of all diseases. Stroke, dementia, epilepsy and Parkinson's disease remain the leading causes of death in the world's population. Over a quarter of a century, the incidence of Parkinson's disease increased by 15.7%, Alzheimer's disease by 2.4%, musculoskeletal system by 3.0%, diseases of the brain and nervous system by 8.9%. (Asqarov I.R, 2023).

Nervousness and similar diseases caused by the tension of the nervous system are one of the most common diseases today. Nervous people quickly get sick due to their anger, blood pressure rises. Changes in the internal organs of such people also occur (Асқаров. И.Р, 2023).

Most EGb 761 clinical trials are targeted at enhancing cognition and memory, with some concentrating on dementia, particularly dementia presentations associated with the gradual loss of cognition and memory, including vascular dementia, Lewy body dementia, and frontotemporal dementia. Because EGb 761 can prevent amyloid production and toxicity, control excitotoxic glutamatergic neurotransmission, and act as a radical scavenger, it could potentially be used to treat multiple dementia etiologies (Nash K. M. 2015). G. biloba improves human cognitive ability when taken, so it remains the main ingredient in many widely used and popular nutritional supplements. Its pharmacological activity depends on two classes - flavonoid glycosides and terpene trilactones (Paul A, 2019). Ginkgo biloba is known to have "memory enhancing" properties. The concentration of flavonoids in the leaves of G. biloba is related not only to the participation of genes, and environmental factors affect the concentration of flavonoids. Among all environmental factors, light and temperature are the most important (Shui-Yuan Cheng, 2009). The organs of this plant, including the leaf, are rich in vitamins, which play an important role in the normal functioning of the central nervous system. For example, vitamin B1 facilitates the use of carbohydrates for energy production, vitamin B12 increases nerve cell viability. The lack of these vitamins leads to peripheral neuropathy (**Baltrusch S. 2021**).

For successful introduction, it is necessary to have up-to-date scientific information about ecological and physiological features, ecological plasticity and adaptive potential of species. High summer temperature, dry air and soil, late spring and early autumn frosts, gas pollution and dusting are the most unfavorable

factors of the habitat of plants in Tashkent and other regions (Fergana Valley and Samarkand) where *G. biloba* was introduced. In the Tashkent region, it was introduced in the Tashkent botanical garden and in the Amir Temur alley of the city of Tashkent, and in the plantations of the Forestry Research Institute in the Fergana Valley (Fergana, Andijan and Namangan regions) and Samarkand regions. The accumulated experience in the introduction of ginkgo biloba (*Ginkgo biloba* L.), a relic of the Mesozoic era in Uzbekistan, indicates the prospects of its cultivation in Uzbekistan for landscaping and the pharmaceutical industry.

We aimed to study the chemical composition of the *G. biloba* tree introduced to Uzbekistan using modern physico-chemical methods and, relying on the obtained research results, to obtain natural medicinal food additives from it and to contribute to the integration of modern medicine with folk medicine.

According to the results of the research obtained with the help of HPLC, it was proved that the leaves of the Defoliation period are also rich in water-soluble vitamins. The HPLC results are tabulated below:

Table 1. Amount and retention times of vitamins in the extract

Vitamins	Retention time (sec)	Concentration mg/l	Amount per 100g sample, mg
Vitamin B ₁	1,966	4,519	11,298
Vitamin B ₉	13,066	100,87	252,175
Vitamin B ₂	15,507	157,94	394,845
Vitamin B ₆	3,633	1,811	4,528
Vitamin B ₁₂	14,485	250,27	625,680
Vitamin C	2,641	6,775	16,938

First of all, we took leaf samples of the acclimatized *Ginkgo biloba* tree in the first fruiting period (summer season) and the plant's seasonal period (autumn season). The amount of important biologically active polyphenols in its content was studied using high-performance liquid chromatography.

In the above chromatogram, the chromatogram of the most important flavonoids content of the leaf samples of the introduced *G. biloba* tree collected during the fruiting period is given using HPLC. The following table shows the results of the research.

Table 2.

Flavonoids of the plant during fruiting period (mg/g)					
Plant part	Gallic acid	Rutin	Quercetin	Apigenin	Kaempferol
Leaves	1,12	0,16	0	0,11	0,02

Defoliation period analysis. Leaf samples were taken in the autumn season of the acclimatized *G. biloba* tree, the period of the end of the annual activity of the plant, and the amount of biologically active important polyphenols in *G. biloba* was studied using high-performance liquid chromatography.

Table 3.

Flavonoids of the plant during defoliation period (mg/g)					
Plant part	Gallic acid	Rutin	Quercetin	Apigenin	Kaempferol
Leaves	0	1,338	0,015	0	0

The results of our studies conducted using HPLC in order to determine the biologically active compounds contained in *G. biloba* leaves are given in the following table:

Limitation. In pathological conditions of the central nervous system, including memory loss, the plant leaf has the property of angioprotector (dilation of capillary blood vessels) (Ажикова А.К. 2020).

As a result of a violation of the oxygen supply of brain cells in the central nervous system, there is a decrease in memory, a weakening of human mental activity, encephalopathy occur. If blood circulation in the brain is normalized in nervous, angry and memory-reducing diseases (Asqarov, I. R, 2023).

Based on the results of the conducted research, neurasthenia, which is common among the population, and encephalopathy, which is causing a big problem for health care professionals and is increasing all over the world, are considered diseases. it leads to the scientifically based conclusion that for the purposes of prevention and treatment of these diseases, it is possible to obtain natural healing and harmless new food supplements based on *G. biloba*. This medicinal plant extract not only improves blood circulation in arteries and veins, but also improves microcirculation (circulation in the capillary blood vessels in the brain), prevents the formation of blood clots, and exhibits antioxidant activity (Koch E. 2005).

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